

Project Management of a Research Internship in Medical Applications

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Abstract

Design and development of medical applications often require a multidisciplinary approach in order to accurately identify the specific needs of customers. Due to the complexity and multiplicity of knowledge and information sources, a structured approach to product design and development of medical applications brings several advantages, specific to the research area, amongst which: standardisation and regulation of preoperative and postoperative medical care of patients, improvement in patient compliance, more accurate medical training materials and devices. The purpose of the current paper is to present in detail a methodology for management and implementation of a research internship as a project that brings together knowledge and competences acquired in medical applications design. The research internship was undertaken within an academic context and environment, based on a structured approach and it applies the basic principles of project management such as project initiation—defining the problem, determining project feasibility by research, planning-monitoring-control, execution and evaluation. This research paper summarizes the background and the purpose of the research internship, describes the process and the methods used to accomplish the tasks by defining the resources, calendar, activity plan and by evaluating the final results at the end of the process.

Keywords: Project Management, Medical Applications, Mandible, 3D Printing.

Introduction

Project management is the discipline which addresses how to initiate, plan, execute, control and conclude the individual or teamwork, in order to achieve specific objectives and key success criteria. Project management involves people able to apply knowledge, techniques, a wide range of skills and tools to meet the requirements of a project. According to Artto A.K (1999) many of the projects that were not completed on time, did not fit in the budget or were not completed to the expected quality, are due to the lack of project management strategy or a project manager able to ensure success by integrating all aspects of the project, bringing together its strengths and weaknesses. Hagan P. (2012) highlighted that the concept of project management is used in a wide array of areas, like engineering, industry, information systems, financial services, medical and health services, commerce, education and training etc.

Payne M.J. et al (2011) underlined that there is little published research and information describing the usage of project management in medical applications due to the pressure of creating an efficient project plan. This entails costs

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and time savings as much as possible, but at the same time with appropriate risk management and quality assessment, to avoid affecting the patient's health and wellbeing.

It is a big challenge to bring together improvements of the healthcare system that haven't been tested before and the patients' life, but studies also show that not just once, the approach of project management in medical applications led to the identification of risks and, thus, managing to implement the project without unfortunate results.

In this case, the aim of the research internship was to design and develop an experimental model of a complete edentulous mandibular bone, using reverse engineering and 3D printing techniques. Research timeframe was set at 4 months by the specificity of the academic agreement. The role of the project manager was assumed by an engineering masters' student. Thus, a list of required abilities has been structured to facilitate the implementation of the projects' aim adapted from Hagan P. (2012), as follows:

- Adapt to and participate in change;
- Problem solve in unfamiliar situations;
- Use a system approach;
- Identify strengths and weaknesses;
- Apply appropriate technical knowledge;
- Have advanced problem-solving, analysis and synthesis skills;
- Ability for engineering design and creativity;
- Be able to think and work individually and in teams;
- Listening, influencing, motivating and communication skills;
- Need for continuous improvement.

Unlike commercial projects or course guidelines, Lopez C. (2010) shows that the project management of an academic research internship is based on two main components: the student's ability to apply all previously acquired knowledge and the skills to understand, analyse and evaluate their own work, submitted throughout the internship. Due to the academic context of the internship implementation, the main project management challenge in terms of resources, tools and techniques used was the structuring and the automation of the process. In terms of innovation, the topic of the internship was considered as the main asset. Nevertheless, the complexity of designing an experimental model of a complete edentulous mandibular bone, together with the limited timeframe and the low medical expertise of the engineering masters' student, made this project a challenge. The current study describes the main project management stages, starting with the idea all the way until developing real medical products, by setting goals, defining key indicators, planning activities, controlling and evaluating the obtained results.

Process Specification and Methods

The research internship was undertaken by an engineering senior masters' student from University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest and it entailed a five-step process flow (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Project management structure adapted from Payne M.J. et al (2011)

The initiation phase represents the answers to few main questions that every project manager must think about such as: Why to create this project? It is feasible? and if so, what it is needed to complete it? Once the project manager got the answers to them all, the project can step forward to the second phase: Planning. The most common method as an answer to all the questions is brainstorming method.

Planning phase, the core of the project management, speaks about creating the team and represents the stage where all the member have to set the main objective of the project, the expected timeframe, budget, individual or group activities, potential risks and backup solutions etc. For the planning stage of the projects, there are several software that can be used such as Microsoft Planner, Windows Primavera etc.

The third phase of project life cycle refers to the execution of all activities defined on the planning stage. The execution is mainly based on the communication and collaboration between all members of the team and each member's sense of responsibility to accomplish the given tasks.

The next phase, monitor and control, represents the responsibility of the project manager to ensure the smoothness of the development of the process in terms of deadlines, costs and efficiency. In order to do it, the project manager can create chat groups, plan meetings or can ask activity reports to each member of the team.

During the last phase, the closure of the project life cycle, represents the simulation of the results and the review of each member's contribution. The results stage can help the project manager to define which were the strengths of the actual strategic plan in order to use them for future projects.

Project Results

Initiation

The project main goal was the design and development of a completely edentulous mandibular bone experimental model by using reverse engineering and additive manufacturing techniques. The developed prototypes aim to be used in academical environment, by the PhD students on the Department of Dentistry, Faculty of Medicine, University of Coimbra, Portugal, as preoperative patterns, in order to simulate the surgeries and so to avoid unfortunate mistakes or complications.

As main partners of the project Department of Dentistry, Faculty of Medicine, University of Coimbra, Portugal together with the Faculty of Biomechanical Engineering, Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Portugal decided to assign the project idea as an internship stage work to a master engineer student, in the role of project manager and they defined the timeframe as being 4 months.

Once assigned the topic and the main roles, a first meeting of the entire team has been planned, in order to introduce the tools and materials that the faculty provided, the offices, laboratories and workplaces where the student together with the whole team could work during his stage.

Planning

From the very beginning, the main partners together with the project manager set the most important objectives of the project such as: MO (main objective): Design and development of a completely edentulous mandibular bone and five secondary objectives: O1. Research of at least 100 scientific papers within 4 weeks on the current state of the art, O2. Converting medical DIICOM data and developing two 3D mandibular masks (trabecular and cortical), O3. Developing two 3D mandibular molds by the end of the 3rd month of the project time, O4. 3D printing of one trabecular and one cortical mold assembly, O5. Developing at least two final prototypes by the end of the internship stage.

In order to ensure a good life cycle of the project and to reach the expected results, a list of possible risks and their contingency plan has been drawn up, forecasting the weight of each of them and it have been allocated grades from 1-3 to describe the level of importance and the impact that can have it on the project life cycle: 1- Low impact; 2- Medium; 3- High impact. The score was calculated by multiplying the contingency grade with the level and importance, the total score showing up the probability that the project to be feasible. Table 1 shows the risks' forecasting of the actual project.

Table 1: Risk analysis

Risk	Objective	Contingency plan	PI	Weight [%]	Score
1. Failure of the 3D printing equipment	O4	The labs are equipped with more than one printer	1	15	0.15
2. Inability to find suitable materials for the injecting process	O5	The Department of Biomedical Engineering provides basic materials such as foam and plastic in order to be able to test the molds and the methodology	3	15	0.45

3. Inability to provide medical data of patients	O2	Using online databases with free medical data access (eg. COCHRANE)	1	10	0.1
4. Risk of delaying the materials delivery	O5	The mold will be tested with the backup materials until the proper delivery	1	10	0.1
5. Risk of FEA simulation results to be different than the real mandibular bone	O5	It will be considered just the methodology of creating the prototypes	2	50	1
*[PI] Potential Impact: 1- Low; 2- Medium; 3- High				100%	1.8

Succeeding the qualitative analysis of the project risks and considering the maximum possible risk value being 4, it has been concluded that the risk incidence rate of the current project is low (1.8).

For a cleaner picture of the steps to follow in order to achieve the main objective, to all the secondary objectives have been allocated a list of activities and responsible members from both main partners of the project. Table 2 represents the human resources list and the distribution of the objectives for each member.

Table 2: Human resources and task distribution

Team members	Task distribution
Project Manager	Managing and organizing O1- O5 activities
Biomechanical Engineer	Ensuring support and overseeing all O1-O5 activities
Dentist	Ensuring support to the researches from O1, Approving the mandibular models from O2 and O5
Dentist Trainee	Ensuring support to the researches from O1 and testing the prototypes of O5
Design Engineer	Ensuring technical support and developing O2, O3 models
Technician	Ensuring technical requirement and support from O2, O3, O4

It is true that the cost, time and quality are predominant criteria to ensure the main scope of the projects, but for a more accurate success, the project manager defined also a list of key performance indicators for each objective such as: KPI₁: one documentation file related to state of the art in additive manufacturing, anatomy of mandibular bone and reverse engineering; KPI₂: two STL masks of mandibular bone parts (trabecular and cortical), KPI₃: two 3D models of trabecular and cortical molds; KPI₄: two 3D printed trabecular and cortical molds; KPI₅: at least two mandibular bone prototypes.

In the end of the internship stage, the project development was examined through the help of this KPI set. Table 3 represents the relations between the objectives and their allocated activities and the KPI.

Table 3: Working plan and relation between objectives and KPI

Main objective: Design and development of a completely edentulous mandibular bone
O1. Research of at least 100 scientific papers within 4 weeks on the current state of the art
KPI*: one documentation file related to state of the art in additive manufacturing, anatomy of mandibular bone and reverse engineering
A1.1. Mandibular bone anatomy
A1.2. Additive manufacturing
A1.3. Reverse engineering techniques
A1.4. Establishing necessary materials and equipment
O2. Converting medical DICOM data and developing two 3D mandibular masks (trabecular and cortical)
KPI: two STL masks of mandibular bone parts (trabecular and cortical)
A2.1 DICOM data processing
A2.2 Desinging two separated masks for the mandibular bone (trabecular and cortical)
A2.3 Creating the STL files of both trabecular and cortical models

O3. Developing two 3D mandibular molds by the end of the 3rd month of the project time
KPI: two 3D models of trabecular and cortical molds
A3.1 Converting and importing the STL files in CAD software
A3.2 Design and development of the trabecular mold
A3.3 Design and development of the cortical mold
A3.4 Grippers simulation
O4. 3D printing of one trabecular and one cortical mold assembly
KPI: two 3D printed trabecular and cortical molds
A4.1 Creating the G codes of the molds
A4.2 3D printing of the trabecular mold
A4.3 3D printing of the cortical mold
A4.4 Grippers acquisition
A4.5 Assembling simulation
O5. Developing at least two final prototypes by the end of the internship stage
KPI: at least two mandibular bone prototypes
A5.1 Acquisition of necessary materials and tools
A5.2 Development by using injection methods of trabecular prototypes
A5.3 Development by injection methods of cortical prototypes
A5.4 Testing the prototypes
*KPI= Key Performance Indicators

For a smoother image of the project development and in order to allocate the costs and the time of each activity, the project manager implemented the Gantt Chart method for the time efficiency and defined a list of expenses as a budget breakdown list. Table 4 represents the Budget breakdown of the project.

Table 4: Budget breakdown

No.	Category	Units	Price [euro]	Total [euro]
1	Personnel expenses			
1.1	Project Manager	16 weeks	10 €/h	3200
1.2	Biomedical Engineer	16 weeks	8 €/h	2560
1.3	Dentist	6 weeks	8 €/h	960
1.4	Dentist Trainee	2 weeks	5 €/h	200
1.5	Design Engineer	2 weeks	8 €/h	320
1.6	Technician	1 week	6 €/h	120
2	Logistics expenses			
2.1	Software license (Materialise Mimics, SolidWorks)	2	2595+1295	3890
2.2	Materials (Polyurethane Foam, Liwuid Plastic)	3	85	255
2.3	Tools (screws, syringe, threaded rod, etc.)		100	100
2.4	Consumables (paper, pens, gloves, lab coats, lab glasses, etc.)		500	500
3	Fixed assets			
	Electricity, water, heat, etc.		1500	1500
			TOTAL	13605

The project was implemented over a period of 4 months (W1 ÷ W16), without working weekends, and the activities were organized in the form of a logical and consistent sequence, assigning a time limit for each of them, as shown in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Gantt Chart

ACTIVITY		START	DURATION [weeks]	W1	W2	W3	W4	W5	W6	W7	W8	W9	W10	W11	W12	W13	W14	W15	W16	
A1	Research of at least 100 scientific papers within 4 weeks on the current state of the art			A1																
A1.1	Anatomy of mandibular bone	W1	4																	
A1.2	Additive manufacturing	W2	1																	
A1.3	Reverse engineering	W3	1																	
A1.4	Establishing necessary materials and equipment	W3	2																	
A2	Converting medical DICOM data and developing two 3D mandibular masks (trabecular and cortical)							A2												
A2.1	DICOM data processing	W5	1																	
A2.2	Designing two separated masks (trabecular and cortical)	W5	3																	
A2.3	Creating the STL models for both trabecular and cortical	W7	1																	
A3	Developing two 3D mandibular molds by the end of the 3rd month of the project time									A3										
A3.1	Converting and importing the STL files	W7	1																	
A3.2	Design and development of customized trabecular mold	W7	2																	
A3.3	Design and development of customized cortical mold	W9	2																	
A3.4	Grippers simulation	W11	1																	
A4	3D printing of one trabecular and one cortical mold assembly												A4							
A4.1	Creating the G codes of the parts	W11	1																	
A4.2	3D printing of trabecular mold	W11	1																	
A4.3	3D printing of cortical mold	W12	1																	
A4.4	Grippers acquisition	W13	1																	
A4.5	Assembling simulation	W13	1																	
A5	Developing at least two final prototypes by the end of the internship stage																A5			
A5.1	Acquisition of necessary materials and tools	W14	1																	
A5.2	Development by injection of trabecular prototype	W14	1																	
A5.3	Development by injection of cortical prototype	W15	1																	
A5.4	Testing the prototypes	W16	1																	

Execution

As a summary of the execution plan, the partners from the Department of Dentistry had to acquire DIICOM data from the computed tomography scan of the patient, which represents the 2D scan images of the mandibular bone of the patient and the first input of the project. Starting with it, they had to share with the master engineering student the personal medical paper of the patient, his anatomical stage and basic details of the research about the medical applications.

The PhD Dentist trainee had to present the requirements of the future mandibular product, to show the techniques and methods of how it will be used, in order to create the hypothesis of the project and to give an overview of the final product to the engineering student. Once them all have been set and the research was ready, the report has been written and the first objective was accomplished. Throughout the research on the anatomy of the mandible, the student developed medical skills and relevant knowledge about the mandibular bone, the meaning of trabecular and cortical part and most important, mechanical properties of each part of the bone, necessary for finding similar materials that can be used to create the experimental model.

Reverse engineering ended up being the most useful way to develop the mandibular model, by starting from the CT scan of the patient, turning it into a 3D model using customized medical software. In order to design the medical data, the biomechanical engineer and the master student defined as tool the medical imaging software Materialise Mimics. The main goal of the activities was to separate the bone in two different masks as trabecular and cortical part. The STL files of the masks have been created and so the second objective was done.

Figure 2: STL trabecular and cortical masks

The next step on the project plan was the development of 3D molds of each mask. The team members that assumed this task were the biomechanical engineer and the master student. Solidworks software was the main used tool for designing and simulating the assembly of the molds and once accomplished, the third objective has been reached.

Figure 3: Trabecular and cortical molds designed in Solid Works

The fourth objective speaks about the 3D printing of the molds. First step was to create the G codes of the files, a data format that can be read by the printing equipment. The 3d printer used was FlashForge Adventurer 3 and the task have been allocated to a team created by the biomechanical engineer, a design engineer and the technician.

Figure 4: 3D printed trabecular mold using FlashForge Adventurer 3 3D printer

The development of the mandibular prototypes, last objective of the project plan, meant to assembly the trabecular mold, to inject the material for the inner surface and so to create the trabecular side, followed by positioning the created part inside the cortical mold and a second injection procedure to be applied with a tougher and stronger material, in order to create the external side. Polyurethane foam and liquid plastic were the chosen materials for the last stage and the task was allocated to the master and the biomechanical engineers.

Figure 5: Mandibular prototypes: a) Polyurethane foam (density 128-240 Kg/m³); b) Liquid plastic; c) Polyurethane foam (density 1080-1230 Kg/m³);

Control and Monitor

The control and monitor part of the project management consisted mainly of meetings organized with all the members involved on the team, status reports were written for all the task of each of the team members, ensuring the closure of the project before the ending of the deadline.

Results

The project has been delivered on time, documentation was written as a final report and it has been presented as a pitch PowerPoint presentation in front of the committee composed by members of the team and one outside teacher from the Department of Biomechanics.

The final products, three models of experimental mandibular bone were created and tested using finite element analysis, in order to see which material is getting closer and responds to the tests the same or most like the mechanical properties of the real mandibular bone.

On the following table is shown the correlation of the results with the defined objectives of the project.

Table 6: Objectives and the correspondent results

Objective	Results
O1. Current state of the art.	R1. Final report and documentation speaking about the usage of additive manufacturing and reverse engineering techniques in medical approaches
O2. Design of medical data	R2. Customised STL files of two separated mandibular masks (trabecular and cortical)/ Mimics Materialise Software
O3. Computer Aided Design of the mold	R3. Two different 3D CAD models / Solidworks Software
O4. 3D printing of the molds	R4. Two separated 3D printed molds using FDM additive manufacturing technologies/ FlashForge Adventurer 3
O5. Development of the final products	R5. Three prototypes/ Polyurethane, Foam & Liquid Plastic

Conclusion

The project management plan led to a successful process, all the objectives have been accomplished without delays or added costs. Regarding the final products, the mandibular prototypes have been used by the PhD Dentistry trainee as samples for surgical simulation and the documentation obtained created a structured methodology of developing anatomical models by using additive manufacturing and reverse engineering techniques that can help both on subject global evaluation and on individual projects' evaluation. These have been adapted to a university context where some specific restrictions existed: professors and students' dedicated time, professors' workload, and diversified nature of the projects. Currently, the products and the process are being used by the dentistry trainees in collaboration with master engineers to develop a customized mandibular pattern that can help prevent unfortunate events during surgical procedures. The products may also allow the comparison between preoperative intervention and the postsurgical results and help the surgeons to receive feedback of their work.

Regarding future research, the methodology of the process to develop mandibular experimental models is open to improvements in terms of time, costs and other materials with more similar mechanical properties in comparison with the real mandibular bone.

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